

ANALYSIS OF SUPPLITIVE VERBS IN OLD ENGLISH AND OLD HIGH GERMAN (BEON AND SÎN/WESAN) AND THEIR COMMON FEATURES

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Abstract: Morphological processes alter a word's root or base, modifying its meaning. The suppletive process, originating from the Latin verb "supleō," can only occur in closed groups. Regular and irregular variants are necessary to explain suppletion. Old English and Old High German share similarities in suppletive verbs. Suffixative verbs derive their grammatical structures from various roots, such as the Old English verb "beon" and Old High German verb "wesan." These verbs have parallel forms and different origins.

Key words: Old English language, old high german language, suppletive verbs, beon/wesan and sîn.

INTRODUCTION.

About supplemental verbs

In order to develop new vocabulary, morphological processes alter a word's root or base, which may modify the word's meaning. One of the two morphological processes that modifies the root or base is the succulent process.

The Latin verb "supleō," whose meaning "to fill; to make whole; to compensate for a loss or deficiency; to add something missing to complete a whole," is where the word "suppletive" originates, according to Veselinova, L.N. [3].

According to Emonds, the suppletive process can only take place in closed groups, and a definition of both the regular and irregular variants is necessary to adequately explain suppletion:

Two words can have regular inflectional forms when the same lexical basis is applied to two distinct contexts using the language's regular phonological and syntactic principles [171].

Important inferences concerning the historical evolution and structural similarity of both languages may be made by comparing the suppletive verbs of Old English and Old High German and thoroughly analyzing the traits they have in common.

A class of verbs known as suffixative verbs derives their grammatical structures from various roots. For instance, the word beon / wesan, which meaning to be, was used in Old English to denote these verbs. The present tense verb beon has parallel forms, is (3rd person singular), and eom (1st person singular), which come from two separate origins. The verb wesan was the source of this word's suppletive form in the past tense [5].

Suppletive Verbs in Old English

Matveeva E. A. argued that the Old English suppletive verbs were derived from many roots rather than just one. The word beon, or wesan, meaning to be, stood up as a subjunctive verb in this abundance of terminology. Verb wesan developed suppletive forms (was, wyron) in the past tense, and parallel forms (eom, is) in the present tense. The fact that this verb has many forms that

originate from two separate roots rather than from one demonstrates the morphological complexity involved in language evolution [35].

Suppletive Verbs in Old High German

As noted by L. I. Moskalyuk and L. V. Kazantseva, there were athematic verbs in Old High German as well, where the personal suffixes were created via straight stem change. For instance, suppletive forms were used in the past to create versions of the verbs *sîn* and *wesan*. Whereas *wesan* generated suppletive types in the past tense, *sîn* possessed forms in the present tense that were derived from other roots [90].

The fact that both languages' subjunctive verbs came from distinct roots suggests that their Germanic ancestry is shared. There are still remnants of the past in both languages.

In terms of structure, Old English *beon/wesan* as well as Old High German *sîn/wesan* are comparable, with the present tense originating from a similar root and the past tense of a distinct root. These forms exhibit complex morphology as well.

Suppletive verbs serve as a visual representation of these linguistic traits, which highlight the complexity and diversity of the language's morphological foundations. At this period, Old English as well as High German both developed similarly, but in their own unique ways.

Ancient languages have retained suffixes as a remnant of their past, a testament to their enduring origins. Simultaneously, the variety of forms is the outcome of inventive methods and represents the interior workings of the language.

A greater knowledge of the morphological components of Old English as well as High German may be gained from this comparison of their respective languages. Old English as well as Old High German verb tenses, known as *präsens* and *präteritum*, respectively, can be compared to learn more about the shared linguistic ancestry and evolution of the two languages. There are clear contrasts and commonalities.

Verb forms in the Present Tense (Präsens) in Old English:

Person/singular

first: *Ic eom, beō*

second person: *þu eart, bist*

third person singular, he/she is, *biþ*

plural: *on, beōþ, we/ge/hi sind* [36].

Old High German language

Singular

first person: *bin, bim*

second person: *bis(t)*

third person: *ist*

Plural: *birut; sint; birum, -n* [91].

There appears to be a tight relationship between the Old English first person singular form *eom* as well as *beō* to the Old High German form *bin*, indicating that the languages have a shared basis. Both *áú eart* (OE) and *áú bist* (OE) also *bis(t)* (OHG) are comparable in the second person singular. Their origins are all in Proto-Germanic ancestry. In Germanic languages, the third person singular is comparable to *is* (OE) and *ist* (OHG). Although the other forms (*on, beōþ, and birum, birut*) are different, Old English *sind* or Old High German *sint* are derived from the same root in the plural.

Verb Forms in the Past Tense (Präteritum) in Old English:

- In the first person singular: "I was" was the *ic*.
- In the second person singular, "you were" (*þu wcre*).
- Third-person singular: *he/o wǵs* - "He was"

We/ge/hi wīron, plural: "They were"[36].

Old High German language:

In the first person singular, it was

In the second person singular: *wāri*

In the third person, singular: *was*

Wârun; wârut; wârum, -n [91].

The identity of the first-person singular variants *was* (OE) as well as *was* (OHG) attests to the Germanic languages' shared ancestry. Although they derive from the same root, the second person

singular forms wūre (OE) while wâri (OHG) are distinct. The third-person singular forms wʃs (OE) and was (OHG) exhibit similarities once more. While wârum and wârut are distinct from the other forms, wʃron (OE) & wârūn (OHG) are comparable plural forms.

The verb forms in Old English as well as Old High German are comparable, supporting the idea that the Germanic languages sprang from a shared source. But because each of them has taken a different developmental route, differences have emerged in various ways. We may observe how ancient languages evolved into current languages by using this comparison.

METHODS

Take into consideration how the word "to be" is used in Beowulf and the Hildebrandslied, bēon and sîn/wesan, respectively, in Old English and Old High German.

Beowulf's verb "to be" (bēon):

10. ofer hronrade hyran scolde,
omban gyldan.

Ðæt wæs god cyning.

Ðæm eafera wæs æfter cenned,

geong in geardum,

þone God sende folce to frofre." [5]

1. **Ðæt wæs god cyning:** The past tense is indicated by "wæs" (a modern form of "was"). "It was a good king" is how this term is translated, and "god cyning" attests to the subject's previous excellence.

2. I'm a little older than before:

Once more, the word "wæs" here denotes a later birthdate for the mirza. The past tense presence is asserted in the statement, which translates as "That heir was born later".

In Beowulf, the past tense word "wæs" is used to qualify or describe a topic. This verb connects the past state or events of the subject and provides context for the events being described [6].

In Hildebrandslied, the verb "sein" (sîn/wesan) means:

25. her was Otachre ummet tirri,
degano dechisto miti Deotrichhe.

her was eo folches at ente: imo was eo fehta ti leap:

chud was her..... chonnem mannum.

ni waniu ih iu lib habbe“..... [229].

1. **her was Otachre ummet tirri:**

In this case, the past tense verb "was" denotes Otachre's condition or position.

2. **imo was eo fehta ti leap:**

The word "was" in this instance denotes the past tense of the conflicts or their features.

3. **chud was her..... chonnem mannum:**

Here, "was" refers to Chud's stressful previous job or circumstance.

In the Hildebrandslied, the word "was" is also employed to characterize things that happened in the past. This verb can also be used to describe the subject's previous behavior or status. [230].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Comparing the verbs bēon in Beowulf and sîn/wesan in the Hildebrandslied:

The verbs "bēon" and "sîn/wesan" are employed in both pieces to characterize circumstances, roles, or attributes from the past. This improves their ability to provide historical knowledge about people or events.

For example, Ðæt wæs god cyning and her was Otachre ummet tirri both assert the quality or position of the subject in the past tense.

The purpose of both verbs is to establish a connection between the subject and predicate. The words "waes" in Beowulf as well as "was" in the Hildebrandslied establish a connection between the topic and other aspects, as well as providing context for the historical events.

For example, Ðæm eafera wæs æfter cenned (Beowulf) and imo was eo fehta ti leap (Hildebrandslied) relate to the state or action of the subject and rely on past events throughout the story.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, these verbs have a shared root with the Germanic languages that originated in Germany and England, and their usage demonstrates how the language of that era portrayed its society and culture. The verb "to be" has two different forms in both works: *bēon* and *sîn/wesan*. These forms serve comparable grammatical and semantic purposes, enabling the creation of a narrative background and subject description. In addition to their grammatical significance, these verbs have historical and cultural significance.

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